

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

POSSIBILITIES OF OBTAINING MINERAL FIBERS BASED ON GABBRO ROCKS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

The article presents the results of a comprehensive physical and chemical study of the gabbro of the Akchinsky deposits. It has been established that the gabbro of this deposit can be used as a raw material for the production of mineral fibers.

Keywords: building material, mineral fiber, igneous rock, gabbro, chemical composition, radiograph, mineralogical composition.

Introduction. Currently, the problem of finding ways to rationally use natural resources, as well as energy saving in modern construction and industry plays an important role. The issues of organizing rational technological processes, saving energy and raw materials are being solved. It should be noted that saving fuel and energy resources, increasing the thermal protection of buildings and structures, the introduction of energy-efficient heat-insulating materials are a priority area that contributes to the development and strengthening of the economic potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In works [1 - 3] it is noted that the priority role in solving the problem of energy saving is the reduction of energy consumption without compromising the quality of products in all industries and the national economy. One of the effective ways to solve this problem is to increase the degree of thermal insulation of residential buildings and various construction projects, which is achieved by the development and production of new efficient types of thermal insulation materials.

The issues of creating and implementing effective import-substituting energy- and resource-saving materials [4, 5] and products based on domestic raw materials come to the fore. These tasks can be solved through the development of innovative technologies for the production of heat-insulating materials, which will ensure demand in the domestic market, will help reduce their imports and create export opportunities. In this regard, materials based on igneous rocks are of great interest. According to expert assessments of exploration works [6, 7], it has now been revealed that the Republic of Uzbekistan has huge reserves of natural raw materials, including deposits of various types of igneous rocks, which can serve as promising raw materials for the production of thermal insulation materials. These include: basalt, diabase - porphyrite, basalt andesite, andesite, gabbro and other igneous rocks.

Material and methods

As a result of the research, it was found that the used igneous rocks differ in their chemical and mineralogical composition and acidity module M_k . In this regard, we have developed criteria for the suitability of these rocks in order to obtain fibers for heat-insulating materials. At the same time, it should be noted that, as the authors of [8, 9] point out, in order to obtain high-quality fibers, various technological approaches and solutions to the raw materials used are required. The properties of products in the form of basalt fibers are determined primarily by the initial chemical composition of the raw material, as well as the acidity modulus M_k . The value of the acidity modulus for basalt one-component charges should be at least 4.0, and sometimes up to 5.5-7.0 [10, 11].

In the course of carrying out research work on the development of compositions, we studied as an object the gabbro of the Akchinsky deposit of the Tashkent region with various concentrations of basic oxides, determined by the chemical-analytical method. To determine the phase composition of gabbro samples from the Akchinsk deposits, the method of X-ray phase analysis was used on an X-ray diffractometer manufactured in Germany Bruker AXS D8-Focus, $CuK\alpha$ radiation, Ni-filter, 40 kV, 40 mA, bit matrix detector LynxEye192, scanning step $0.01^\circ 2\theta$, scanning speed 0.05 s/step.

All samples were surveyed under constant conditions. International reference books of X-ray powder diffraction patterns were used in the calculations and in the identification of phases.

Results and discussion.

As a result of the research, the material composition and acidity modulus of the studied samples of gabbro (AG-1, AG-2, AG-3) from the Akchinsky deposits were determined (Table 1).

Table 1

Results of the chemical analysis of the studied samples of gabbro-basalt rocks

Name of samples	Mass content of oxides, %, in air-dry substances									M_k
	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	SO ₃	п.п.п.	
AG-1	49,82	15,83	13,02	4,58	7,32	2,59	2,71	1,28	2,81	5,50
AG-2	51,62	16,53	11,15	4,53	7,28	2,45	2,48	1,14	2,87	5,77
AG-3	52,02	15,74	11,65	4,43	6,97	2,38	2,66	1,23	2,92	5,94

As can be seen from the data in Table. 1, a comparison of the chemical compositions of the studied samples of the samples showed that the gabbro of the Akchinsky deposit consists mainly of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, MgO, CaO, Na₂O and K₂O oxides, as well as indicators of the acidity modulus Mk, which ranges from 5.50 to 5.94. In [12-14], the most optimal for obtaining basalt fibers is the chemical composition that provides the value of the acidity modulus from 5.0 to 7.0. It is noted that the higher the value of the acidity

modulus, the more resistant to moisture the resulting fiber based on basalt and basalt-like raw materials.

Important technological parameters for the production of basalt fibers are the initial tc.pl and the final tc.pl. melting temperature of raw materials. These values indirectly characterize the energy consumption for melt production. The results of studies carried out on experimental samples of rocks of the indicated deposits are given in table. 2.

Table 2

Name of samples	Temperature, °C	
	T_{imp}	T_{fmp}
AG-1	1195	1300
AG-2	1190	1290
AG-3	1190	1295

As can be seen from Table. 2, samples of gabbro-2 samples with the chemical composition SiO₂ -51.62 are characterized by the lowest melting range; Al₂O₃-16.53; Fe₂O₃-11.15; MgO-4.53; CaO-7.28; Na₂O-2.45 and K₂O-2.48. Accordingly, the melt preparation time for production and energy consumption for melting the basalt charge will be lower. The initial melting temperature of all the samples under study is in the range of 1190-1195°C, the final temperatures are not more than 1300°C.

X-ray phase analysis of all prototype gabbro samples from the Akchinskoye deposit shows the presence of diffraction reflections of quartz d= 0.425; 0.336; 0.244; 0.229; 0.213; 0.211; 0.198; 0.182; 0.179; 0.154; 0.145 nm; chlorite d=0.710; 0.460; 0.454; 0.403; 0.388; 0.364; 0.313; 0.296; 0.284; 0.264; 0.252; 0.244; 0.238;

0.229; 0.210; 0.171; 0.145 nm; albite d = 0.641; 0.403; 0.375; 0.364; 0.347; 0.336; 0.320; 0.317; 0.313; 0.294; 0.284; 0.264; 0.252; 0.238; 0.229; 0.213; 0.210; 0.201; 0.181; 0.178; 0.171; 0.154; 0.145 nm; amphibolite d=0.902; 0.879; 0.403; 0.388; 0.336; 0.313; 0.312; 0.305; 0.294; 0.244; 0.238; 0.229; 0.210; 0.201; 0.187; 0.177; 0.171; 0.145 nm; calcite d=0.388; 0.305; 0.249; 0.229; 0.210; 0.148; 0.145 nm.

The obtained results of material and X-ray phase analysis of the studied gabbro samples from the Akchinsky deposit (Table 3) showed that their chemical and mineralogical composition is similar and consists mainly of minerals of quartz, chlorite, albite, calcite, as well as other minerals, the content of which is very small. and small amounts.

Table 3

Name of samples	Mass content of minerals, %					
	quartz	albite	calcite	amphibolite	illite	chlorite
AG-1	1,76	91,38	1,47	3,08	0,01	2,03
AG-2	1,33	91,89	1,42	3,17	traces	2,19
AG-3	1,58	91,65	1,50	3,01	0,02	2,24

The results of the mineralogical analysis show that in all test samples the content of feldspar minerals - albite is in large quantities.

Conclusion. Thus, as a result of a comprehensive study of chemical and mineralogical compositions, as well as by determining the acidity modulus index (Mk) using chemical, X-ray phase analysis, it was found that the studied gabbro-basalt rocks of the Akchinsky deposit can be recommended as the main raw material for the production of basalt mineral fibers. Therefore, with such indicators of the acidity modulus, they are suitable for obtaining basalt fibers according to the standard.

In addition, the use of the investigated igneous raw materials of Uzbekistan for the development of the composition and production of basalt fibers will expand the raw material base for the production of heat-insulating materials for various purposes.

References

1. Gorelik P. I., Zolotova Yu. S. Modern heat-insulating materials and features of their application // Construction of unique buildings and structures. 2014. №. 3 (18). pp. 5 - 8.
2. Schiavoni S., Alessandro F. D, Bianchi F., Asdrubali F. Insulation materials for the building sector: A review and comparative analysis // Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews. 2016. No. 62. P. 988 - 1011.
3. Jelle B. P. Traditional, state-of-the-art and future thermal building insulation materials and solutions – properties, requirements and possibilities // Energy Build. 2011. No. 43. P. 2549 - 2563.
4. Gorlov Yu. P., Merkin A. P., Ustenko A. A. Tekhnologiya teploizolyatsionnykh materialov: ucheb. for universities. Moscow: Stroyizdat, 1980. 339 p.
5. Buratti C., Moretti E., Belloni E., Agosti F. Thermal and acoustic performance evaluation of new basalt fiber insulation panels for buildings // 6th International Building Physics Conference, IBPC. Energy

Procedia. 2015. No. 78. P. 303 - 308.

6. Ergeshov A. M., Fimushkin L. I. Geological and economic monitoring of the state and use of the mineral resource base of non-metallic raw materials in Uzbekistan. Tashkent, 2005. 161 p.

7. Musaeov R. A. Gabbro of the Akchinsky intrusion as a petrological raw material: author. dis. ... cand. geol. - mineral. Sciences. Tashkent, 1998. 26 p.

8. Singha K. Short a Review on Basalt Fiber // International Journal of Textile Science. 2012 No. 1(4). R. 19 - 28

9. Shevchenko V. P., Tokunov S. G., Gulamova D. D., Kim R. B. Development of technology for the production of basalt fiber based on mineral raw materials of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its use in the energy sector. tr. Rep. scientific and technical conf. "Actual issues of innovative technology for the development of chemistry and the food industry and oil and gas processing." Tashkent, 2011. S. 218 - 219.

10. Perevozchikov B. V. Preliminary review of the suitability of mafic rocks from the northern part of the Tagil zone of the Urals for high-tech production of

basalt fiber. Bulletin of the Perm University. Geology. 2009. Issue. 11. S. 36 - 45.

11. Khakberdiev N. M., Khamidov R. A. Methodological approaches to the selection and preliminary assessment of the suitability of rocks of the main composition for obtaining basalt fiber. sci.-tech. conf. "Integration of science and practice as a mechanism for the effective development of the geological industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan." Tashkent, 2016. S. 55 - 58.

12. Tatarintseva O. S., Zimin D. E. Peculiarities of melting of rocks and fiber formation from melts // Polzunovskiy vestnik. 2006. No. 2. S. 158 - 162.

13. Niyazova Sh. M., Kadyrova Z. R. Usmanov Kh. L., Khomidov F. G. Chemical and Mineralogical Studies of Magmatic Rocks of Uzbekistan for Obtaining Heat-Insulating Materials // Glass Ceram. 2019. V. 75, No. 11 - 12. P. 491 - 495.

14. Pat. Gutnikov S.I., Lipatov Ya.V., Lazoryak B.I., Avdeev V.V. RU 2540676. Method for producing continuous fiber based on basalt. Published 02/10/2015. Bull. No. 4.